

Synthesis of bicyclic γ -lactam derivatives by intramolecular carbene insertion and aza-Wittig reaction[†]

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Manuscript received 27 June 2013, accepted 28 June 2013

Abstract : A comparative study of the various methodologies to construct bicyclic γ -lactams is reported. Thus Rh^{II}-catalyzed decomposition of 2-pyrrolidone and pyrrolidine derived diazomalonates were attempted to synthesize fused γ -lactams. Spectral evidences revealed the formation of diastereomeric alcohols instead of desired C-H or N-H insertion products, indicating significant conformational bias towards insertion process. On the other hand, the method involving the N-H insertion onto the lactam nitrogen of 2-pyrrolidone ring was successful. Intramolecular aza-Wittig reaction was also successfully explored to construct bicyclic γ -lactam scaffolds. All the bicyclic analogues showed weak antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

Keywords : Gamma-lactam, carbene, aza-Wittig, intramolecular, insertion, antibacterial.

Introduction

The effectiveness of the β -lactam antibiotics has been challenged by rapid evolution of β -lactamase enzymes in some bacteria, which catalyze the hydrolytic destruction of β -lactams¹. Extensive work on the synthesis and chemical modification of β -lactam antibiotics over the years has produced a wide variety of biologically active analogues and novel structural entities in this area². In view of the relatively limited possibilities left for structural and functional variations of the β -lactam motif while maintaining a rational approach to the accepted modes of antibacterial action, chemists have turned their attention to explore the γ -lactams and related heterocyclic compounds³ as potential antibacterial agents. Three disconnection pathways **a**, **b** and **c** can be thought of for the synthesis of bicyclic γ -lactam derivatives starting from L-pyroglutamic acid (Scheme 1). Amongst these, the pathways **a** and **b** involve the well-exploited carbene insertion⁴ reaction (intramolecular N-C or C-C bond formation). The other pathway **c** involves the Wittig-type olefination⁵. We have attempted all the three pathways and in this paper, we describe our findings.

Scheme 1. Retrosynthesis of bicyclic γ -lactams.

Results and discussion

Towards exploring the pathway **a**, the tosylate **10** (available from L-pyroglutamic acid) was malonylated by refluxing with ethyl malonyl chloride in dry benzene. Diazo transfer at the active methylene of the resulting **11** was accomplished by treatment with methanesulphonyl azide⁶ and Et₃N in dry CH₂Cl₂. The resulting diazo compound **12** was reacted with Rh₂(OAc)₄ in dry CH₂Cl₂ at room temperature⁷. Chromatography over Si-gel afforded a mixture of diastereomeric alcohols **1a** and **1b**; no bicyclic C-H insertion product could be isolated (Scheme 2).

Having failed to do a C-H insertion reaction, we then looked into the possibility of N-H insertion. Thus the

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Reagents and conditions : (a) TsCl, Et₃N, dry DCM, 0 °C, rt, 4 h (88%); (b) Ethyl malonyl chloride, dry C₆H₆, reflux, 2 h (85%); (c) Mesityl azide, dry Et₃N, dry DCM, 25 °C, 6 h (75%); (d) Rh₂(OAc)₄, dry DCM, 25 °C, 3 h (80% overall)

Scheme 2. Carbene insertion in L-pyroglutamate systems.

tosylate **11** was converted to azide **13** by heating with NaN₃ in dry DMF at 50 °C. This was reduced with H₂/10% Pd-C in presence of (Boc)₂O in dry ethyl acetate to furnish the desired Boc derivative **14** (Scheme 3). Diazo transfer at the active methylene of **14** with methanesulphonyl azide and Et₃N in dry acetonitrile, followed by reaction of the resulting diazo carbamate **15** with Rh₂(OAc)₄ in dry CH₂Cl₂ at room temperature or in refluxing benzene, gave a similar mixture of diastereomeric alcohols **2a** and **2b**. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the mixture showed a pair of doublets, which after D₂O exchange, became a pair of singlets (Fig. 1). These were attributed to the active methine flanked between the two carbonyl systems. Presence of peaks at *m/z* 345 (MH⁺) and *m/z* 367 (MNa⁺) in the mass spectrum of the mixture also supported the formation of such alcohols. Reaction of the diazosulfonamide **17** with Rh₂(OAc)₂ also yielded a simi-

Fig. 1. Effect of D₂O shake on mixture of **2a** and **2b**.

lar mixture of diastereomeric alcohols **3a** and **3b** (Scheme 3).

These results could be rationalized by considering the conformations of the intermediate rhodium carbenoids⁸. The preferred conformation of the intermediate rhodium carbenoid is the one that avoids unfavorable dipole repulsion between the two carbonyl groups. Muthusamy *et al.* during their study of carbene insertion on unsubstituted

Reagents and conditions : (a) NaN₃, dry DMF, 50 °C, 12 h (75%); (b) H₂/(10%) Pd-C, (Boc)₂O, dry EtOAc, rt, 3 h (85%); (c) (i) TFA, dry DCM, 0 °C, 1 h, (ii) NsCl, Et₃N, dry DCM, 0 °C, 20 min (70% overall); (d) Mesityl azide, dry Et₃N, dry DCM, rt, 4 h (70% for both **15** and **17**); (e) Rh₂(OAc)₄, dry DCM, 25 °C, 3 h

Scheme 3. Attempted carbene insertion in protected amines.

pyrrolidone derivatives, also reported the formation of similar mixture of alcohols⁹.

To check whether the oxo functionality of the lactam ring is the only parameter that is causing the failure for C-H or N-H insertion, the 2-pyrrolidone ring was replaced by pyrrolidine ring, which would possibly alleviate the conformational constraint. Thus the carbene insertion reaction was attempted on L-proline-derived diazomalonates **20** and **23** (Scheme 4). Their reaction with $\text{Rh}_2(\text{OAc})_4$ in dry CH_2Cl_2 at room temperature, however, again yielded a mixture of alcohols **4a/4b** and **5a/5b**. Thus, apart from the dipolar repulsion between the

two carbonyls as was present in 2-pyrrolidone derivatives, some other factors, possibly the repulsion between the two substituents in pyrrolidine systems, may also be contributing to the conformational bias.

After all these failures in inducing C-H insertion, the construction of the second ring via N-H insertion onto the lactam nitrogen (route **b**) of preformed 2-pyrrolidone ring was undertaken¹⁰. Thus, ester **25** was prepared by malonylating the alcohol **24** (Scheme 5). TFA-mediated deprotection, followed by diazo transfer, produced our desired diazo compound **27** which on treatment with $\text{Rh}_2(\text{OAc})_4$ in dry DCM at room temperature furnished

Reagents and conditions : (a) Ethyl malonyl chloride, dry Et_3N , dry DCM, 0 °C, 1 h (70%); (b) Mesyl azide, dry Et_3N , dry DCM, rt, 4 h (75% for **20** and 65% for **23**); (c) $\text{Rh}_2(\text{OAc})_4$, dry DCM, 25 °C, 3 h; (d) TBAF, dry THF, 0 °C, 1 h (70%); (e) Benzoyl chloride, dry Et_3N , cat DMAP, dry DCM, 0 °C, rt, 2 h (75%).

Scheme 4. Carbene insertion in L-proline derivatives.

Reagents and conditions : (a) Ethyl malonyl chloride, dry Et_3N , dry benzene, reflux, 2 h (70%); (b) TFA, dry DCM, 0 °C, 1 h (95%); (c) Mesyl azide, dry Et_3N , dry DCM, rt, 4 h (75%); (d) $\text{Rh}_2(\text{OAc})_4$, dry DCM, 25 °C, 3 h (55%)

Scheme 5. Carbene insertion at NH.

the bicyclic compounds **6a** and **6b**, isolated as a diastereomeric mixture (1 : 1 ratio). These were fully characterized by ^1H NMR, ^1H COSY, ^{13}C NMR and mass spectral data.

Aza-Wittig reaction⁵ is another important tool for C–N bond formation. It has been widely explored to construct various *N*-containing heterocyclic framework¹¹. Compound **13** contained both the carbonyl and azide functionalities, perfectly crafted, to generate a 5-5 or 5-7 fused bicyclic γ -lactam derivative which made us interested to evaluate the outcome of an intramolecular aza-Wittig reaction on **13**. Thus Ph_3P was added at room temperature to a solution of **13** in anhydrous benzene under high dilution condition (0.005 *M*). After stirring at room temperature for 2 h, the mixture was refluxed for 6 h more (Scheme 6). Desired cyclic product **7** was separated from triphenylphosphine oxide by simple crystallization from ether-hexane solvent system, in essentially pure form. The 5-5 fusion in **7** was confirmed from X-ray crystallographic analysis (ORTEP structure shown in

hydrogens were done from their crosspeaks with hydrogen attached to **C5** as recorded in ^1H COSY spectrum (Fig. 3). The **NH** and **H9** hydrogens were found to be exchangeable with D_2O . Encouraged by this result, we had also attempted to synthesize a 5-6 fused γ -lactam using similar strategy. For that we synthesized compound **29** from azide **28**. Compound **29**, on triphenylphosphine-mediated intramolecular aza-Wittig reaction serendipitously produced compound **8**. The aza-Wittig reaction was found to involve concomitant oxidation of the CH_2 group adjacent to the ring fusion nitrogen. Compound **8** was purified by column chromatography (Si-gel, EtOAc).

The structure of compound **8** was confirmed on the basis of NMR and mass spectral data. In the ^{13}C NMR spectrum, the three carbonyl signals appeared at δ 173.7, 170.2 and 157.5 ppm. The DEPT-135 spectrum contained only 4 methylene signals. The HMBC spectrum (Fig. 4) indicated cross peak between the newly formed carbonyl and the olefinic hydrogen. HRMS spectrum tallied with the molecular formula : calculated for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Na}$

Reagents and conditions : (a) Ph_3P , dry benzene, rt (2 h), reflux (6 h) (80% for **7** and 40% for **8**); (b) NaH , THF, 0 $^\circ\text{C}$, 15 min (77%)

Scheme 6. Aza-Wittig reaction.

Fig. 2)¹². ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR assignments for each of the hydrogens and carbons present in **7** were done analyzing the ^1H COSY, DEPT-135, HMBC and HSQC spectra. For example, assignments of the **H6** and **H4**

Fig. 2. X-Ray structure of **7**.

Fig. 3. ^1H -COSY spectrum (expanded, 400 MHz) of **7** in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 4. HMBC spectrum (expanded, 400 MHz) of **8** in CDCl_3 .

$[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 261.0851, found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 261.0851. The ease of oxidation is probably driven by the formation of the captodatively stabilized radical **8A**. A tentative mechanism is given below (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7. Tentative mechanism.

Ph_3P , being a reductant, possibly assisted the reduction of **8B** to **8C** during the process. The mechanism of aerial oxidation is similar to those put forward for aerial oxidation of aldehydes¹³.

Antibacterial activity was checked in DMSO solution using disc diffusion assay¹⁴ technique against ampicillin sensitive *E. coli* and *S. aureus* strains with ampicillin as standard. A negative control disc without any sample but impregnated with equivalent amount of solvent (DMSO) was also used in the assay. Compounds (**6a**+**6b**) exhibited only 25% antibacterial activity with respect to ampicillin against both the strains, whereas compounds **7** and **8** showed less than 20% activity. The poor activity might be due to the solubility problem (especially for **7** which is only partly soluble in DMSO). Attempted hydrolysis of the ester functionality in **7** and **8** led to decomposition of starting materials. We are currently addressing to solve

this issue by employing a different ester protecting group.

Experimental

^1H NMR (400 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz) were recorded on a Bruker NMR spectrometer. ^2H -chloroform was used as solvent unless otherwise mentioned. The peak at δ 7.26 was taken as reference. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ unit and ^1H - ^1H coupling constants in Hz. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer instrument (Spectrum RX-73713) using KBr pellet for solids and neat for liquids. The characteristic peaks are expressed in cm^{-1} . All the dry solvents used for reactions were purified according to the standard protocols. Benzene and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were distilled from sodium-benzophenone under an atmosphere of dry argon/nitrogen. Chloroform and dichloromethane (DCM) were dried over phosphorous pentoxide. Ethanol and methanol were dried first over calcium oxide and then magnesium turnings.

Triethylamine and *n*-butyl amine were distilled over KOH. Dimethylformamide was dried by azeotropic removal of water with benzene, followed by distillation over calcium hydride. Potassium carbonate was dried by frying under vacuum.

Synthesis of 3-oxo-3-[2-oxo-5-(toluene-4-sulfonyloxy-methyl)pyrrolidin-1-yl]-propionic acid ethyl ester (**11**) :

Into a solution of 5-[2-(toluene-4-sulfonyl)-ethyl]-pyrrolidin-2-one (**10**, 1.076 g, 4 mmol) in dry benzene (30 mL), ethyl malonyl chloride (0.615 mL, 4.8 mmol) was added and reaction mixture was then refluxed for 1.5 h. Reaction was quenched at room temperature with saturated aqueous NaHCO_3 solution, extracted three times with EtOAc, organic part was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation in vacuum gave a yellow oil which was purified by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) to furnish

11; yield 85%; oil; $[\alpha]_D^{28.0}$: (-) 47 (c 1, CHCl₃); v_{\max} (neat): 1678, 1167; δ_H : 7.76 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.36 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.53 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.35 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8, 3.6 Hz), 4.19–4.13 (3H, m), 3.90, 3.63 (2 × 1H, AB_q, *J* 16.4 Hz), 2.81 (1H, m), 2.49 (1H, m), 2.46 (3H, s), 2.22 (1H, m), 2.09 (1H, m), 1.25 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 175.3, 166.8, 166.4, 145.3, 132.2, 130.1, 127.8, 69.5, 61.3, 55.2, 44.1, 31.9, 21.6, 20.3, 14.0; Mass (ESI): *m/z* 384 [MH⁺]; HRMS (ESI): *m/z* calcd. for C₁₇H₂₂NO₇S: [M+H]⁺ 384.1117, found [M+H]⁺ 384.1114.

General procedure of diazo transfer reactions:

A flame-dried, two-necked flask equipped with a N₂ inlet and septum was charged with malonates (2.6 mmol), methanesulfonyl azide [*Caution: Although we have never had any trouble with mesyl azide, it is potentially explosive!*] (2.9 mmol, 1.1 eq) and CH₃CN (5 mL). To this solution was added triethylamine (5.3 mmol, 2 eq). The reaction was followed by TLC. Typically, it was complete in 3–6 h. The mixture was diluted with 10% aqueous NaOH and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 20 mL). The combined organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated in vacuum. The residual oil was purified by flash chromatography (Si-gel, hexane: EtOAc) to yield the desired α -diazo esters.

General procedure for rhodium(II)-catalyzed intramolecular cyclization reactions of α -diazo esters:

To an oven-dried flask containing a DCM solution of the appropriate diazo compound (1.0 mmol, final concentration 0.005 M) was added 5 mol% of rhodium(II) acetate dimer catalyst under an argon atmosphere at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred and monitored by ¹H NMR until starting material disappeared. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude residue was purified by flash chromatography (Si-gel, hexane: EtOAc).

2-Diazo-3-oxo-3-[2-oxo-5-(toluene-4-sulfonyloxy-methyl)pyrrolidin-1-yl]-propionic acid ethyl ester (12):

Yield 75%; oil; v_{\max} (neat): 2155, 1680; δ_H : 7.72 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.32 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.50–4.48 (1H, m), 4.38 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8, 3.6 Hz), 4.24 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz), 4.10 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8, 2.0 Hz), 2.66 (1H, m), 2.48 (1H, m), 2.42 (3H, s), 2.21 (1H, m), 2.08 (1H, m), 1.28 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 174.0, 160.7, 160.6, 132.2, 129.9, 127.8, 69.0, 61.8, 55.8, 31.4, 21.6, 20.3, 14.2;

Mass (ESI): *m/z* 410 [MH⁺].

2-Hydroxy-3-oxo-3-[2-oxo-5-(toluene-4-sulfonyloxy-methyl)pyrrolidin-1-yl]-propionic acid ethyl ester (1a):

Yield 40%; oil; $[\alpha]_D^{28.0}$: (-) 27.1 (c 1, CHCl₃); v_{\max} (neat): 3360, 1659, 1166; δ_H : 7.72 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.36 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 5.20 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz), 4.42 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8, 3.2 Hz), 4.25–4.19 (2H, m), 4.16 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8, 2.0 Hz), 3.82 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 2.84 (1H, m), 2.50 (1H, m), 2.46 (3H, s), 2.31 (1H, m), 2.16 (1H, m), 1.29 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 176.0, 169.5, 167.7, 145.7, 131.9, 130.1, 127.8, 73.3, 69.3, 62.1, 55.6, 31.7, 21.6, 21.1, 13.9; Mass (ESI): *m/z* 422 [MNa⁺], 400 [MH⁺], 382 [MH⁺-H₂O], 326 [MH⁺-CO₂Et]; HRMS (ESI): *m/z* calcd. for C₁₇H₂₂NO₈S: [M+H]⁺ 400.1066, found [M+H]⁺ 400.1063.

2-Hydroxy-3-oxo-3-[2-oxo-5-(toluene-4-sulfonyloxy-methyl)pyrrolidin-1-yl]-propionic acid ethyl ester (1b):

Yield 40%; oil; $[\alpha]_D^{28.0}$: (-) 31.5 (c 1, CHCl₃); v_{\max} (neat): 3380, 1660, 1159; δ_H : 7.77 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.35 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 5.36 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 4.59 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz), 4.57–4.21 (3H, m), 4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 10.4, 2.4 Hz), 4.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 2.83 (1H, m), 2.51 (1H, m), 2.45 (3H, s), 2.30 (1H, m), 2.17 (1H, m), 1.28 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 175.9, 169.4, 167.6, 145.4, 132.1, 130.0, 127.9, 73.3, 68.8, 62.1, 55.3, 31.5, 21.6, 20.9, 13.9; Mass (ESI): *m/z* 422 [MNa⁺], 400 [MH⁺], 382 [MH⁺-H₂O], 326 [MH⁺-CO₂Et]; HRMS (ESI): *m/z* calcd. for C₁₇H₂₂NO₈S: [M+H]⁺ 400.1066, found [M+H]⁺ 400.1063.

Synthesis of 3-[2-(tert-butoxycarbonylaminoethyl)-5-oxo-pyrrolidin-1-yl]-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (14):

To a solution of compound **14** (763 mg, 3 mmol) in EtOAc (25 mL) was added 10% Pd/C (100 mg), and di-*t*-butyl dicarbonate (770 μ L, 3.6 mmol) and the mixture was stirred under hydrogen (1 atm) for 4 h at room temperature. The catalyst was filtered off on celite and washed with EtOAc. After evaporation to EtOAc, the resulting liquid was purified by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane: EtOAc = 1:1); yield 70%; oil; $[\alpha]_D^{28.0}$: (-) 73.5 (c 1, CHCl₃); v_{\max} (neat): 1744, 1703, 1367, 1334, 1276, 1202, 1166; δ_H : 5.09 (1H, s), 4.46 (1H, m), 4.20 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz), 4.15, 3.70 (2 × 1H, AB_q, *J* 16.4 Hz), 3.54–3.44 (2H, m), 2.69 (1H, m), 2.49 (1H, m), 2.16–

2.04 (2H, m), 1.43 (9H, s), 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 175.9, 167.5, 166.5, 156.4, 79.4, 61.3, 57.1, 44.1, 41.8, 31.8, 28.2, 20.8, 13.9; Mass (ESI) : m/z 329 [MH⁺]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for C₁₅H₂₅N₂O₆ : [M+H]⁺ 329.1713, found [M+H]⁺ 329.1715.

2-Diazo-3-{2-[(2,2-dimethylpropionylamino)-methyl]-5-oxo-pyrrolidin-1-yl}-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (15) :

Yield 70%; oil; ν_{\max} (neat) : 1744, 1702, 1367, 1532, 1352, 1166; δ_H : 5.12 (1H, s), 4.50 (1H, m), 4.29 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 3.45–3.43 (2H, m), 2.62 (1H, m), 2.50 (1H, m), 2.19 (1H, m), 2.01 (1H, m), 1.43 (9H, s), 1.31 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 174.7, 161.9, 161.2, 156.4, 79.7, 61.9, 57.7, 42.5, 31.9, 28.3, 21.1, 14.3; Mass (ESI) : m/z 355 [MH⁺].

Synthesis of 3-{2-[(4-nitrobenzenesulfonylamino)-methyl]-5-oxo-pyrrolidin-1-yl}-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (16) :

To a solution of compound **16** (656 mg, 2 mmol) in dry DCM (20 mL) at 0 °C was added trifluoroacetic acid (191 μ L, 2.5 mmol) and reaction mixture was stirred for 20 min. DCM was evaporated under reduced pressure; resulting mass was washed with (3 \times 5 mL) dry benzene and dried under high vacuum. The dry salt was immediately dissolved in dry DCM (15 mL), cooled to 0 °C, triethylamine (418 μ L, 3 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 5 min. Then solution of *p*-nitrobenzene sulphonyl chloride (2.0 mmol) in dry DCM (5 mL) was added dropwise. Reaction was quenched with water after 10 min, extracted with DCM, washed with water, brine solution, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation in vacuum gave an oil, from which the desired sulphonamide was isolated by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1); yield 70%; oil; $[\alpha]_D^{28.0}$: (–) 90.2 (c 1, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) : 1744, 1703, 1367, 1334, 1276, 1202, 1166; δ_H : 8.35 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.02 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 6.03 (1H, dd, J 9.6 Hz), 4.50 (1H, m), 4.40, 3.47 (2 \times 1H, AB_q, J 16.4 Hz), 4.28–4.19 (2H, m), 3.43 (1H, m), 3.16 (1H, m), 2.90 (1H, m), 2.55 (1H, m), 2.33–2.17 (2H, m), 1.31 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 175.9, 169.2, 166.8, 150.0, 145.6, 128.1, 124.5, 62.2, 55.8, 44.7, 44.0, 32.0, 20.5, 14.0; Mass (ESI) : m/z 436 [MNa⁺], 414 [MH⁺]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for C₁₆H₂₀N₃O₈S : [M+H]⁺ 414.0971, found [M+H]⁺ 414.0974.

2-Diazo-3-{2-[(4-nitrobenzenesulfonylamino)-methyl]-5-oxo-pyrrolidin-1-yl}-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (17) :

Yield 70%; oil; ν_{\max} (neat) : 2148, 1735, 1729, 1654, 1531, 1351, 1166; δ_H : 8.34 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.00 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.21 (1H, m), 4.51 (1H, m), 4.35–4.24 (2H, m), 3.26–3.21 (2H, m), 2.75 (1H, m), 2.51 (1H, m), 2.26 (1H, m), 2.09 (1H, m), 1.32 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 174.4, 161.9, 161.5, 150.0, 145.8, 128.1, 124.4, 62.3, 56.5, 45.4, 31.7, 21, 14.2; Mass (ESI) : m/z 440 [MH⁺].

Synthesis of 3-[2-(tert-butyldiphenylsilyloxymethyl)-pyrrolidin-1-yl]-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (19) :

Into solution of 2-(tert-butyldiphenylsilyloxymethyl)-pyrrolidine, **18** (1.25 g, 3.69 mmol) and Et₃N (0.77 mL, 5.53 mmol) in dry benzene (20 mL) was added ethyl malonyl chloride (566 μ L, 4.4 mmol) and reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. Reaction was quenched at room temperature with 5% aq. NaHCO₃ solution, extracted three times with EtOAc, organic part was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation in vacuum gave an yellow oil which was purified by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 3 : 2); yield 70%; oil; $[\alpha]_D^{28.0}$: (–) 40.3 (c 1, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) : 1665; δ_H : 7.65–7.61 (4H, m), 7.45–7.36 (6H, m), 4.27 (1H, m), 4.21–4.12 (2H, m), 3.84–3.74 (2H, m), 3.50 (1H, m), 3.45–3.32 (3H, m), 2.12–1.81 (4H, m), 1.27–1.22 (3H, m), 1.05 (9H, s); δ_C : 167.8, 165.1, 135.5, 133.5, 132.8, 130.0, 129.6, 127.8, 64.8, 61.3, 59.3, 48.0, 42.7, 28.0, 26.8, 24.1, 19.2, 14.1; Mass (ESI) : m/z 476 [MNa⁺], 454 [MH⁺], 376 [MH⁺-Ph]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for C₂₆H₃₆NO₄Si : [M+H]⁺ 454.2414, found [M+H]⁺ 454.2417.

3-[2-(tert-Butyldiphenylsilyloxymethyl)-pyrrolidin-1-yl]-2-diazo-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (20) :

Yield 75%; yellow liquid; ν_{\max} (neat) : 2085, 1667; δ_H : 7.66–7.11 (4H, m), 7.43–7.33 (6H, m), 4.37 (1H, m), 4.28–4.21 (2H, m), 3.76 (2H, m), 3.60 (1H, m), 3.48 (1H, m), 2.10–2.04 (2H, m), 1.95 (1H, m), 1.77 (1H, m), 1.27 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.05 (9H, s); δ_C : 162.0, 159.8, 135.5, 133.4, 133.3, 129.7, 129.6, 129.5, 127.7, 127.6, 127.5, 67.2, 63.8, 61.2, 59.3, 49.7, 27.3, 26.8, 19.2, 14.4; Mass (ESI) : m/z 480 [MH⁺]; HRMS (ESI) :

m/z calcd. for $C_{26}H_{34}N_3O_4Si$: $[M+H]^+$ 480.2319, found $[M+H]^+$ 480.2315.

Synthesis of 3-(2-hydroxymethylpyrrolidin-1-yl)-3-oxopropionic acid ethyl ester (21) :

To a solution of silyl ether **19** (650 mg, 1.43 mmol) in THF at 0 °C was added dropwise a solution of tetrabutyl ammonium fluoride hydrate (588 mg, 1.86 mmol) solution in 10 mL THF. As soon as TLC indicated disappearance of starting material (3 h), reaction mixture was concentrated under vacuum at room temperature and the resulting semi-solid mass was purified by chromatography (Si-gel, Eluent-EtOAc); yield 70%; pale yellow liquid; v_{max} (neat) : 3406, 1660; δ_H : 4.21 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 3.73 (1H, dd, J 11.2, 2.8 Hz), 3.68–3.45 (4H, m), 3.43 (2H, s), 2.78 (1H, bs), 2.05 (1H, m), 1.96 (1H, m), 1.87 (1H, m), 1.68 (1H, m), 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 167.3, 166.9, 66.1, 64.2, 61.4, 61.3, 45.8, 41.9, 28.2, 14.2; Mass (ESI) : m/z 216 $[MH^+]$; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $C_{10}H_{17}NO_4$: M^+ 215.1158, found M^+ 215.1156.

Pyrrolidin-2-yl methyl ester (22) :

Into solution of benzoyl chloride (139 μ L, 1.2 mmol) in dry pyridine (5 mL) at 0 °C was added a solution of alcohol **21** (212 mg, 1 mmol) in dry pyridine (2 mL), and the reaction was stirred at room temperature for 10 h, pyridine was then evaporated under vacuum, resulting mass was dissolved in 50 ml EtOAc; organic layer was washed successively with 10 mL each of 5% aq. HCl solution, 5% aq. $NaHCO_3$ solution, water and brine, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation in vacuum gave an oil which was purified by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 2 : 3); yield 75%; white liquid; v_{max} (neat) : 1715, 1667; δ_H : 8.03–8.01 (2H, m), 7.58 (1H, m), 7.48–7.43 (2H, m), 4.54 (1H, m), 4.47–4.42 (2H, m), 4.22–4.15 (2H, m), 3.59–3.49 (2H, m), 3.42 (2H, s), 2.08–1.97 (4H, m), 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 166.3, 162.4, 160.4, 132.9, 131.1, 129.8, 128.4, 64.4, 61.5, 61.3, 56.6, 49.7, 27.9, 24.7, 14.4; Mass (ESI) : m/z 320 $[MH^+]$; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $C_{17}H_{22}NO_5$: $[M+H]^+$ 320.1498, found $[M+H]^+$ 320.1494.

Pyrrolidin-2-yl methyl ester (23) :

Yield 65%; oil; v_{max} (neat) : 2112, 1710, 1665; δ_H : 8.04 (2H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 7.56 (1H, t, J 7.6 Hz), 7.44 (2H, t, J 7.6 Hz), 4.62 (1H, m), 4.49–4.46 (2H, m), 4.26–

4.21 (2H, m), 3.65 (1H, m), 3.51 (1H, m), 2.02–1.80 (4H, m), 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 166.4, 161.9, 160.5, 133.0, 130.0, 129.7, 128.4, 67.6, 64.3, 61.3, 56.7, 49.7, 27.8, 24.7, 14.4; Mass (ESI) : m/z 368 $[MNa^+]$, 346 $[MH^+]$.

3-[2-(tert-Butyldiphenylsilyloxy)methyl]-pyrrolidin-1-yl]-2-hydroxy-3-oxopropionic acid ethyl ester (4a/4b) :

δ_H : 7.66–7.56 (4H major + 4H minor, m), 7.45–7.38 (6H major + 6H minor, m), 4.90 (1H minor, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.79 (1H minor, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.72 (1H major, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.28 (1H minor, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.25–4.15 (4H (major + minor), m), 4.14–3.75 (6H (major + minor), m), 2.15–2.07 (4H minor), 1.99–1.86 (4H major, m), 1.29 (3H major, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.20 (3H major, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.06 (9H major + 9H minor, s); Mass (ESI) : m/z 470 $[MH^+]$; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $C_{26}H_{35}NO_5Si$: $[M+H]^+$ 470.2364, found $[M+H]^+$ 470.3294.

1-(2-Ethoxycarbonyl-2-hydroxyacetyl)-pyrrolidin-2-yl methyl ester (5a/5b) :

δ_H : 8.04–7.98 (4H, both isomer, m), 7.60–7.55 (1H major + 1H minor, m), 7.47–7.42 (2H major + 2H minor, m), 4.82–4.79 (1H major + 1H minor, m), 4.58–4.49 (2H major + 2H minor, m), 4.38 (1H minor, dd, J_1 9.2, J_2 3.6 Hz), 4.29–4.19 (3H major + 2H minor, m), 4.13 (1H major, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.07 (1H minor, d, J 9.2 Hz), 3.81–3.73 (2H minor, m), 3.68–3.59 (2H major, m), 2.13–1.98 (4H major + 4H minor, m), 1.30 (3H major, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.18 (3H major, t, J 7.2 Hz); Mass (ESI) : m/z 335 $[MH^+]$; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $C_{17}H_{21}NO_6$: $[M+H]^+$ 336.1448, found $[M+H]^+$ 336.2199.

Synthesis of malonic acid 1-tert-butoxycarbonyl-5-oxopyrrolidin-2-yl methyl ester ethyl ester (25) :

To a solution of 2-hydroxymethyl-5-oxo-pyrrolidine-1-carboxylic acid *tert*-butyl ester **24** (655 mg, 3 mmol) and Et_3N (0.63 mL, 4.5 mmol) in dry benzene (20 mL) was added ethyl malonyl chloride (461 mL, 3.6 mmol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. Reaction was quenched at room temperature with 5% aq. $NaHCO_3$ solution, extracted three times with EtOAc, organic part was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation in vacuum gave a yellow oil which was purified by column chromatography (Si-

gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1); yield 70%; oil; ν_{\max} (neat) : 1658, 1640; δ_{H} : 4.44–4.36 (2H, m), 4.29 (1H, dd, J 10.8, 2.4 Hz), 4.12 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 3.39 (2H, s), 2.65 (1H, m), 2.43 (1H, m), 2.18 (1H, m), 1.95 (1H, m), 1.52 (9H, s), 1.27 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_{C} : 174.0, 166.2, 166.1, 149.7, 83.5, 65.7, 61.8, 56.0, 41.5, 31.6, 28.0, 20.8, 14.1; Mass (ESI) : m/z 330 [MH^+]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{NO}_7$: [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 330.1553, found [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 330.1555.

Synthesis of malonic acid ethyl ester 5-oxo-pyrrolidin-2-yl methyl ester (26) :

To a solution of ester **25** (658 mg, 2 mmol) in dry DCM (20 mL) at 0 °C was added trifluoroacetic acid (191 mL, 2.5 mmol) and reaction mixture was stirred for 35 min. DCM was evaporated under reduced pressure; resulting mass was washed with (3 \times 5 mL) dry benzene and dried under high vacuum; yield 95%; state thick liquid; ν_{\max} (CHCl_3) : 1662; δ_{H} : 6.87 (1H, bs), 4.26 (1H, m), 4.20 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.05–4.00 (2H, m), 3.41 (2H, s), 2.42–2.26 (3H, m), 1.85 (1H, m), 1.27 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_{C} : 173.4, 166.5, 166.3, 67.5, 61.8, 53.1, 41.2, 22.7, 14.0; Mass (ESI) : m/z 230 [MH^+]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_5$: [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 230.1029, found [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 230.1025.

Synthesis of 2-diazo-malonic acid ethyl ester 5-oxo-pyrrolidin-2-yl methyl ester (27) :

Yield 65%; yellow solid; ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2125, 1660; δ_{H} : 6.03 (1H, bs), 4.42 (1H, dd, J 10.4, 2.8 Hz), 4.23 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.04–3.94 (2H, m), 2.46–2.04 (3H, m), 1.86 (1H, m), 1.32 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_{C} : 178.0, 161.3, 160.5, 67.8, 61.8, 52.8, 29.5, 23.1, 14.3; Mass (ESI) : m/z 255 [MH^+].

Synthesis of 3,6-dioxo-hexahydro-pyrrolo[2,1-c][1,4]oxazine-4-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (as mixture of diastereomers 6a and 6b) :

Yield 55%; oil; ν_{\max} (neat) : 1690, 1660; δ_{H} : 4.77 (1H, s), 4.38–4.24 (3H, m), 4.06–3.95 (2H, m), 2.51–2.35 (2H, m), 2.27 (1H, m), 1.81 (1H, m), 1.31 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_{C} : 179.0, 178.9 (for two isomer), 168.4, 168.2 (for two isomer), 168.1, 168.0 (for two isomer), 72.0 (for both isomer), 68.5, 68.4 (for two isomer), 62.6, 62.5 (for two isomer), 52.8 (for both isomer), 22.6, 22.5 (for two isomer), 14.0 (for both isomer); Mass (ESI) : m/z 268 [$\text{MNa}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$], 246 [$\text{MH}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$], 228 [MH^+],

182 [$\text{MH}^+ - \text{EtOH}$]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_5$: [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 228.0872, found [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 228.0872.

Synthesis of 3-(2-azidomethyl-5-oxo-pyrrolidin-1-yl)-3-oxo-propionic acid ethyl ester (13) :

Sodium azide (520 mg, 8.0 mmol) was added under argon to a solution of **11** (767 mg, 2.0 mmol) in DMF (12 mL). The mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 18 h and then diluted with EtOAc (100 mL), washed with water (3 \times 20 mL) and brine (25 mL), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation in vacuum gave oil, from which the desired azide was isolated by Si-gel column chromatography (eluent : EtOAc); yield 85%; oil; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28.0}$: (–) 71.8 (c 1, CHCl_3); ν_{\max} (neat) : 2110, 1645; δ_{H} : 4.51 (1H, m), 4.19 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 3.93, 3.88 (2 \times 1H, AB_q, J 13.2 Hz), 3.81 (1H, dd, J 12.8, 4.8 Hz), 3.57 (1H, dd, J 12.4, 2.4 Hz), 2.83 (1H, m), 2.51 (1H, m), 2.20 (1H, m), 1.99 (1H, m), 1.27 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_{C} : 175.5, 166.9, 166.4, 61.3, 55.6, 52.8, 44.2, 31.7, 21.0, 14.0; Mass (ESI) : m/z 255 [MH^+]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$: [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 255.1093, found [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ 255.1095.

General procedure of intramolecular aza-Wittig reaction :

Into a solution of azide derivative (1 eq) in anhydrous benzene (final concentration 0.005 M) was added triphenylphosphine (1 eq). The mixture was stirred at ambient temperature till TLC indicated disappearance of starting azide derivative. Then the mixture was refluxed to complete the intramolecular aza-Wittig reaction. Solvent was removed under vacuum and the resulting mass was purified either by simple crystallization or by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc or MeOH : CHCl_3).

Synthesis of (5-oxo-hexahydro-pyrrolo[1,2-c]imidazol-3-ylidene)-acetic acid ethyl ester (7) :

Yield 90%; white crystalline solid; m.p. 135 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28.0}$: (–) 102.1 (c 1, CHCl_3); ν_{\max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1703, 1663; δ_{H} : 7.41 (1H, bs), **5.32** (1H, s), 4.49 (1H, m), 4.15–4.07 (2H, m), 3.74 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 3.25 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.84 (1H, m), 2.64 (1H, m), 2.39 (1H, m), 1.93 (1H, m), 1.25 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_{C} : 171.0, 171.1, 153.0, 71.5, 59.4, 58.9, 49.9, 36.6, 26.9, 14.6; Mass (ESI) : m/z 233 [MNa^+], 229 [$\text{MH}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$], 211 [MH^+]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$:

$[M+H]^+$ 211.1083, found $[M+H]^+$ 211.1083.

Synthesis of 4-(2-azidomethyl-5-oxo-pyrrolidin-1-yl)-3-oxo-butyric acid ethyl ester compound (29) :

To a suspension of sodium hydride (60% suspension in mineral oil, washed with dry petroleum ether to remove the oil, 600 mg, 25 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml), a solution of azide **28** (700 mg, 5 mmol) in 5 ml dry THF was added dropwise at 0 °C and it was stirred for 30 min at 0 °C. Then ethyl-4-chloroacetoacetate (770 μ L, 6 mmol) dissolved in dry THF was added dropwise. The mixture was stirred for 15 min at 0 °C. Evaporation in vacuum gave a solid mass which was quenched with NH_4Cl , extracted with EtOAc. Organic layer was washed with brine, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation in vacuum gave oil from which the desired compounds were isolated by Si-gel column chromatography (hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 2); yield 77%; oil; v_{max} (neat) : 2120, 1670; δ_H : 4.51, 4.15 (2 \times 1H, AB_q, J 13.2 Hz), 4.23–4.18 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 3.82 (1H, m), 3.55 (1H, dd, J 12.8, 4.0 Hz), 3.53, 3.47 (2 \times 1H, AB_q, J 16.0 Hz), 3.40 (1H, dd, J 12.8, 5.2 Hz), 2.56–2.39 (2H, m), 2.30 (1H, m), 1.83 (1H, m), 1.29 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 197.5, 175.8, 166.7, 61.6, 57.2, 53.5, 50.6, 46.6, 29.3, 22.1, 13.9; Mass (ESI) : m/z 291 [MNa⁺], 269 [MH⁺]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $C_{11}H_{17}N_4O_4$: $[M+H]^+$ 269.1250, found $[M+H]^+$ 269.1252.

*Synthesis of (4,6-dioxo-hexahydropyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazin-3-ylidene)-acetic acid ethyl ester (8) :*

Yield 55%; yellow liquid; v_{max} (neat) : 1715, 1655; δ_H : 8.37 (1H, bs), 5.74 (1H, s), 4.26 (1H, m), 4.18–4.13 (2H, m), 3.61 (1H, m), 3.27 (1H, t, J 12 Hz), 2.57 (2H, dd, J 11.2, 5.2 Hz), 2.29 (1H, m), 1.79 (1H, m), 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz); δ_C : 173.7, 170.2, 157.5, 147.4, 89.7, 59.7, 55.9, 45.6, 30.9, 22.8, 14.3; Mass (ESI) : m/z 261 [MNa⁺], 239 [MH⁺]; HRMS (ESI) : m/z calcd. for $C_{11}H_{14}N_2O_4Na$: $[M+Na]^+$ 261.0851, found $[M+Na]^+$ 261.0851.

Acknowledgement

Author AB thanks DST, Government of India for a research grant. DST is also thanked for providing funds for 400 MHz NMR facility under the IRPHA programme and single crystal X-ray facility under the FIST programme. BR, IH, DG and PSA are grateful to CSIR,

Government of India for a Senior Research Fellowship. Dr. M. Bhattacharjee is thanked for crystal structure analysis. Dr. S. K. Ghosh is thanked for antibacterial activity testing. Selected NMR and mass spectra are available in the supporting information section.

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